

APPENDIX: MEASUREMENT ITEMS

1. TOE FRAMEWORK

1.1. Technological dimension

1.1.1. Relative advantage

- RA1. Data analytics allow companies to make the right decisions and take the right actions.
- RA2. Data analytics improve the quality of decisions and actions.
- RA3. Data analytics enable decisions and actions to be performed more quickly.

1.1.2. Compatibility

- COM1. Use of data analytics fit into our working style.
- COM2. Use of data analytics is completely compatible with our current company operations.

1.1.3. IT infrastructure

- IT-IN1. The company has been using data analytics applications.
- IT-IN2. The company has been using data collection applications.
- IT-IN3. The company has been using a data analytics application to manage employees.

1.2. Organizational dimension

1.2.1. Top management support

- TMS1. Top management creates support for data analytics initiatives within the organization.
- TMS2. Top management promotes data analytics as a strategic priority within the organization.
- TMS3. Top management is interested in the news about using data analytics.

1.2.2. Human resource capabilities

- HRC1. Employees have the knowledge and technical capabilities corresponding to the requirements of data analytics.
- HRC2. Employees could lead the process of designing and developing data analytics applications.
- HRC3. Employees have business understanding compatible with business requirements regarding the use of data analytics.
- HRC4. Employees have the right skills to accomplish their data analytics tasks successfully.
- HRC5. Employees hold suitable work experience to accomplish their data analytics tasks successfully.
- HRC6. Employees are well trained to accomplish data analytics tasks.

1.3. Environmental dimension

1.3.1. Competitive pressure

- CP1. This company is experiencing competition intensity to implement data analytics.
- CP2. This company will face competitive disadvantage if it does not use data analytics.

1.3.2. Security and privacy concerns

- SPC1. This company faces trust issues in data management by the data analytics system.
- SPC2. Data that are transferred / analyzed in data analytics applications might not be secure.
- SPC3. Data that are saved and used from data analytics applications might lack confidentiality and privacy.

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2. ORGANIZATIONAL ANALYTICS MATURITY

2.1. Organization

- ORG1. We have both business and IT sponsorship across the company for data analytics initiatives.
- ORG2. The company has a data analytics roadmap in place that has been agreed to and the discipline to change the roadmap as needed.
- ORG3. The company takes action towards using big data (i.e., analytics, as part of a process, as part of a business model, etc.).
- ORG4. The company has a well-defined funding process in place for big data and big data analytics.
- ORG5. Data analysis funding has moved out of IT and into the business (and is not bootstrapped).
- ORG6. In this company, data drives our business.

2.2. Infrastructure

- INF1. The company uses repeatable processes and tools for big data and big data analytics development.
- INF2. The company has the right skills in place to address new big data infrastructure technologies for its big data efforts.
- INF3. The company is trying to adapt quickly to changes by modifying its technological infrastructure concerning data analytics.

2.3. Data management

- DMAN1. The company effectively integrates all types of data that it collects.
- DMAN2. The company analyzes all type of data it collects.
- DMAN3. The company has methods in place to process big data as it enters its environment.
- DMAN4. The company uses an Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system to manage part or all its operations.

2.4. Analytics

- ANL1. The company has a big, well established, data analytics team (i.e., data scientists, business analysts, computer scientists, etc.).
- ANL2. The company has users across the spectrum of analytic skills, making use of big data analytics.
- ANL3. The company utilizes all kinds of data in its big data analytics efforts. This includes unstructured as well as structured data, real-time data, and data from external and internal sources.
- ANL4. The company utilizes advanced analytics, such as predictive analytics and other data mining or advanced statistical techniques, as part of its big data efforts.
- ANL5. The company is implementing big data analytics because it is a cost saving process.
- ANL6. The company is implementing big data analytics because it is improving the decision-making process.

2.5. Governance

- GOV1. The company's big data management and analytics policies are in place and documented.
- GOV2. Data ownership and access policies are clearly in place.
- GOV3. The company has put in place methods and policies to deal with big data retention issues.
- GOV4. The company's security policies are in place and enforced for all forms of data.
- GOV5. The company's security measures are in place to deal with data access.

3. HR ANALYTICS ADOPTION

- HRA1. The HR department regularly imports and analyses data in the HR analytics context.
- HRA2. The HR department regularly uses HR analytics for its processes.
- HRA3. The HR department consults the results of the HR analytics for decision-making.
- HRA4. The HR department uses and relies on the results of HR analytics for decision-making.